

Effect of Flooding on Socio-Economic Wellbeing of Residents in Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt Local Government Areas, Rivers State.

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Abstract

Flood devastation has been the reoccurrence incidence in Niger Delta, which may be as a result of current and ugly problem of global warming, hitherto ravaging the world, which has always left the victim helpless in the face of wrecked socioeconomic development. The study examines the effect of flooding on socioeconomic development of Port Harcourt and Obio Akpor Local Government Areas. To established facts, the study used descriptive statistics, chi square, and analysis of variance for analysis of data. It was revealed that the residents are familiar with the problems, however, majority of them do not have access to radio sensitisations and material prints distributed when it occurs. It further established that the flood affected negatively social amenities, business owners, destroyed properties, and hampered movements. This is affirmed with the flooding having significant effects on school, electricity, and income of businesses of the citizens. The study concluded that flooding has devastating effect on the socioeconomic wellbeing of Rivers State citizens. It recommends that the citizens should strictly build project in line with government directives and avoid blocking drainages. Besides, government enact strict laws on flooding; federal and state government should be proactive on flood operation and emergency response.

Keywords: Flooding, Socio-economic, Development, Wellbeing, Port Harcourt

INTRODUCTION

There were numerous obstacles to Rivers State's social and economic well-being. The majority of these cities are also characterized by unchecked growth, poor and inadequate housing, inadequate infrastructure, bad planning and administration, weak urban governance, and inefficient land use structure that leads to slums. Cities around Nigeria, especially those in Rivers State, are plagued by these numerous issues. Socioeconomic development is the process of enhancing the well-being of people, families, communities, and societies by promoting economic growth, lowering poverty, and guaranteeing sustainable development, according to the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (2021). Similarly, Organisation for Economic Corporation and Development (OECD) (2021) defines it as indicator in assessing a country's progress and often addresses income distribution, poverty rates, and access to essential services. It is crucial for sustainable and inclusive development because it eradicate poverty, promote prosperity, and ensure wellbeing for all. Besides, it is the integral part of these goals including targets related to poverty reduction, quality education, decent work, radical inequalities, and sustainable cities (United Nation, 2021).

Furthermore, flooding which is an overflowing of a great body of water over land is the one of the major environmental issues/crises in this century that affect socioeconomic development. There is no doubt that the world is under serious threat. From the United States of America to China, United Kingdom to Nigeria, analysts have argued that the environment is responding to the abuses heaped on it by man's activities, (Christopherson, 1997). The complexity of anthropogenic activities of man without adequate attention to geological structure of most cities of developed and developing nations has undoubtedly contributed to reoccurrence of disaster and consequently poses threat to environmental sustainability in most of these nations (Oludare et al., 2018). Flooding is associated with extreme weather events resulting from general rise in sea level globally due to global warming as well as the saturated nature of the wetlands (Umana, 2019). Most of the Niger Delta States and Cities are within the mangrove and fresh water belt, experience annual flooding or sometimes that are devastating to socio economic development. It is against the study focused assessing the effect of flooding on the socioeconomic wellbeing Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt Local Government Area in Rivers State

LITERATURE REVIEW

The relevant theories, concepts and studies are reviewed to necessitated the gap(s), its justification, and discussion of the findings.

Urban Resilience to Floods Theory

Urban resilience to floods theory sees floods as the capacity of a city to tolerate flooding and to reorganize, should a physical damage and socioeconomic disruption occur, so as to prevent deaths and injuries and maintain current socioeconomic identity. It can be conceptualized as the capacity to remain in a desirable regime while experiencing a flood. The desirable regime is considered as a set of variables reflecting aspects such as livelihood security, economic performance, and mobility that collectively represent the city's socioeconomic identity (Adger, 2000; Cumming et al., 2005; Gunderson, 2010). Urban resilience to floods is measured by the flood magnitude the city can undergo until it reaches a threshold and shifts to an undesirable regime. This theory suggests flood adaptations, and it challenges the conventional wisdom that cities cannot live without flood control. The development of this theory is based on an attempt to enrich the existing body of resilience theory through focusing on a specific type of system with a specific problem (Kuei-Hsien Liao, 201; Berkes, 2007). The idea of resilience has a long history in ecology and engineering, but its application to natural hazard management is relatively recent. What defines resilience to floods remains ambiguous, despite the increasing attention given to the concept of resilience in flood hazard management. Urban built environment and riverine flooding to develop a theory on urban resilience to floods . There are two major resilience interpretations-engineering resilience and ecological resilience (Holling, 1996). In order to operationalize the theory for planning practices, a resilience surrogate measure is proposed for assessing urban resilience to floods.

Ecological Resilience Theory

Urbanised flood plains are such systems, where climate, socioeconomic trends, built systems, and riverine processes affect flood hazards and disasters. They operate like evolving ecosystems rather than engineering systems and are characterised by complex behaviours associated with nonlinearity, emergence, uncertainty, and surprise (Liu et al., 2007). Such dynamic systems will not stay at a predetermined state. To be sure, moving quickly from a chaotic state to an organised one after a disaster is paramount, but it is unconstructive to restore the pre-disaster socioeconomic activities and built environments that are vulnerable in the first place (Klein et al. 2003). What remains unchallenged in this recovery notion is the preoccupation with stability. Stability becomes problematic when forced at temporal and spatial scales, at which the system is inherently dynamic (Cumming et al., 2006). The ecological resilience concept is a more appropriate framework for flood hazard management, for it builds on a more realistic paradigm of multi-equilibrium, focusing pragmatically on persistence in a world of flux (Adger et al., 2005). The ecological resilience Concept has become a sophisticated resilience theory, addressing complex human-nature couplings. It is instrumental for addressing flood hazards that arise from the interaction between riverine and urban dynamics.

Concept of Flood

A Flood is an Overflow of water that submerges land spaces that are usually dry; it may also be referred to as an inflow of tide. Consequently, floods are the most common type of disaster worldwide and he also mentions the three major types being categorized as river floods, flash floods and coastal floods (Smith, 1999). Ward (1978) argues the types of floods in this fashion is the flash floods which are associated with violent, convectional storms which are of the short duration, and is measured in minutes not hours. These types of floods occur everywhere in the world; in addition, there are also single event floods which have a substantially longer duration than flash floods and result from a variety of rainfall conditions in which widespread rains of several hours or days can move over a drainage basin, which are commonly associated with cyclonic storms.

Causes of Flood

The rate of rainfall explains the intensity; the duration is how long the rain continues and the blockage of the drainage system by continuous dumping of refuse or solid waste. Flash floods take a few minutes or hours to develop after an intense rainfall or failure of a dam or levee, or sudden release of water held by ice or debris jam. These floods can catch people unprepared (Master cited in Disaster, 2007). Champ (1983) stresses that flooding causes peril, but also has benefits for people. People use flood plains for agriculture which flourishes on rich alluvial soil that has been washed down by the flooding rivers, of which, one third of the world's population still depend for their food. While Malele (2009) argues that poor urban governance often makes urban dwellers, their properties and the environment more vulnerable to the impacts of a number of hazards like flooding, diseases, fire and pollution. There are various factors that enhance flooding, these include; the degree of urbanization, lack of vegetation cover

due to deforestation, land development; presence of impermeable soils and existence of low-lands (Roger, et al., 2017). Flooding is caused climatologically, which may be in the form of excessively prolonged rainfall or melting ice. Some of the floods are not directly caused by climatology, for example from excessive high tides associated with storm-surge effects caused by a combination of very low barometer pressure and high wind speeds; others are caused by earthquakes, landslides or failure of dams and other control works (Ward, 1978).

Effects of Flooding

Wisner et al. (2007) say that flooding has shown a remarkable impact internationally and locally-Nigeria-the damage which has been costly to even developed countries like Australia and Europe. The disasters caused by floods affect not only individuals but also governments, planners and insurers. They cause more economic losses than any other hazards. In addition, Maosong, et al. 2008) and Miller (1997) say flooding is taken as the second largest meteorological environmental disaster in China, and has detrimental effects on people's lives. Besides, Smith and Aizeselu (1990) reports that flood disaster in Kano occurrence in 1988 greatly destroyed lives and properties including the Baguda dam project. The flood was caused by intense rainfall leading to generation of tremendous overland flow. This is was different flooding in the central Nigerian plateau state that killed 39 persons. Heavy rainfall caused the lamingo dam to overflow near Jos, sweeping across a number of neighbourhoods in Jos, and approximately 200 homes were submerged or destroyed and 3,000 people left homeless (BBC, 2012).

Empirical Literature

Chiadikobi, Omoboriowo, Chiaghanam, Opatola, and Oyebanji (2011) undertook a study on Flood Risk Assessment of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The study found out that the rapid rates of urbanization and population growth of Obio/Akpor & Port Harcourt city in the last fifteen years have led to uncontrolled and uncoordinated development of swamps, floodplains and natural drainage channels thereby aggravating the risk of flood hazards in the city. It equally established that the rainfall intensity is high in Port Harcourt due to climatic changes such as high rainfall volume and duration. The result of this study showed that the risk of the occurrence of potentially damaging flood in Port Harcourt increases with increasing rainfall intensity. Also, the risk of flood is bound to increase in the future with increasing urbanization.

Thecla, Akukwe, and Ogbodo (2015), spatial analysis of vulnerability to flooding in Port Harcourt metropolis, Nigeria. The study analyzed the vulnerability to flooding in Port Harcourt metropolis, Nigeria by creating vulnerability indices and comparing these indices across the thirteen zones that make up Port Harcourt metropolis. The integrated vulnerability assessment approach using indicators was used. The indicators were grouped into adaptive capacity, sensitivity and exposure based on the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2007). The data on these indicators were obtained from field work, questionnaire and map measurements. PCA was performed to obtain the first component scores which were used to weight the variables before calculating the vulnerability indices of the 13 zones. The vulnerability indices result show that Mgbuosimiri (Zone K) is relatively the most vulnerable while the least vulnerable is Eligbolo (Zone D). Cluster analysis was used to group the different vulnerability indices to produce a vulnerability map showing the spatial pattern of the different flood vulnerability levels (i.e., very high, high, low and very low vulnerability levels). The spatial pattern of the vulnerability levels increases towards the North West, south west, south and north east, and decreases towards the central of Port Harcourt.

Akukwe and Krhoda, (2018) evaluated the effects of flooding on food security in agrarian communities of south eastern Nigeria. The study focused on eight (8) agrarian communities that are vulnerable to flooding in the south eastern region of Nigeria known for its comparative advantage in the production of yam, sweet potatoes and cassava which are also staples. The principal component analysis (PCA) extracted three components of Eigen values >1 explaining 68.02% of the total variance, thus summarizing these negative effects of flooding on food security in three (3) aspects namely; food supply and distribution; household income and investment; and farm labor and facilities.

Thecla and Akukwe (2014) studied the determinants of flooding in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Nigeria. The study used descriptive analysis; it revealed that the urbanization aggravates flooding by limiting where run-off can flow and the increased impervious layers in urban areas obstruct the natural channel thereby shortening the time taken by flood water to flow into river. Besides, heavy rainfall was ranked the first and second respectively. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) showed that the poor drainage quality and low-lying topography explained greatly the causes of flooding in the metropolis.

Emberga (2014) assessed the causes and effects of flood in south western Nigeria Read literature on floods. Using qualitative and quantitative analyses, it is established that no city or town of the south western Nigeria is absolutely free from floods in any year. The numbers of occurrences, magnitudes, affected area and adverse socio-economic consequences have been increasing over the year. In the same vein, Oladokun and Proverbs (2016) conducted study on flood risk management (FRM) practices in Nigeria. The systematic review was used to evaluate several past flood events and associated responses. The study revealed that absence of integrated FRM systems, lack of inter-agency coordination, substandard and weak infrastructures, inadequate drainage network, high urban poverty, low level literacy, cultural barriers, and weak institutions characterize current FRM practices.

Nkwunonwo, (2016) examined the flooding and flood risk reduction in Nigeria. The prevalence of flooding within Nigeria, using critical narrative review. The study established that the climate change and poor urban planning is issue of critical for flooding. Over the period 1985 to 2014, frequent floods are recorded in Niger, Adamawa, Oyo, Kano and Jigawa states possibly due to the influence of rivers Niger, Benue, Ogun and Hadeja. Besides, Lagos state seems to have experienced most of the floods in the country. In addition, rapid population growth, urbanization and flooding in the country have greatly human lives and properties at critical dimensions. Furthermore, poor awareness of the hazard is a major impasse towards its management, which created a significant gap in the knowledge of how to improve on the current efforts towards addressing the challenges of flooding in Nigeria; therefore, the attempts to tackle the hazard appear to be limited.

METHODOLOGY

The study area is Obio/Akpor and Port-Harcourt Local Government Area (LGA) of Rivers State. The state's LGAs are regarded as the major urban centres of economic activities in Nigeria, and one of the major cities of the Niger Delta region. The LGA covers 260 km² with a population of 3,464,789 persons (National Population Commission, 2006). It is located at latitude: 4.902909 longitude: 4⁰54'10.47254 nUTM Easting: 278, 354. 40. The population of Port Harcourt is at 1,382,592 with a growth rate at 2.9% which would estimate to about 5,865,000 individuals or more; it includes Obio/Akpor local government area's who are directly or indirectly affected by the flooding, which have an estimated figure of 25482 individuals. The study used survey design and the sample population comprised of 100 respondents selected randomly from different communities/locations in Obio/Akpor Local government and Port-Harcourt metropolis, capturing the affected communities in the study area. Data used in this work came from primary sources. The primary data would be obtained through administered questionnaires, personal observation and interviews granted. The method of analysis includes, descriptive statistics, chi-square, analysis of variance (ANOVA).

RESULT

The analysis and reporting of the results are presented as follows:

Table 1 Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents in Port Harcourt and Obio-Akpor

Characteristics	Frequency (n=100)	Percentage (%)	Mean
Male	49	49.00	
Female	51	51.00	
Total	100	100.00	
Age			
19-29 Years	23	23.00	
30-39 Years	31	31.00	
40-49 Years	20	20.00	39
50-59 Years	23	23.00	
60 Years and above	3	3.00	
Total	100	100.00	
Marital status			
Single	17	17.0	
Married	33	33.0	
Divorced	36	36.0	
Widowed	14	14.0	
Total	100	100.0	
Level of Education			

Primary Education	11	11.0
Secondary Education	31	31.0
Tertiary Education	58	58.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2019

From Table 1, majority of the respondents (51%) were female, while (49%) were male. this implying that the population in the study area is dominated by female. Majority of the respondents (31%) were between the ages of 30-39 years. this implying that the community is dominated by young and vibrant persons. 36% of the respondents reported being married while 33% reported being single. The implications are that the institution of marriage is still held high in the study area. Majority (58%) of the respondents reported having tertiary education as the highest-level education.

From other analysis starting from the resident being familiar with flooding problems; the study affirmed that 100% of the residents in Port Harcourt and Obio-Akpor LGA are familiar with the flooding problems-they either reside in Eneka, Elelenwo, Peter Odili Road or Ozuoba which means they have a good idea about the flood situation in the affected areas. Besides, for the awareness 88% of the respondent said they aware while 12% of the respondent said otherwise. Consequently, the results from the field survey indicated that none of the respondents are members of any flood awareness groups aware of the existence of any such groups/organizations, while their access to radio sensitisation is 36% as against 64% that does not access to it. Flooding constantly occurring in the study area is a serious problem, displacing residents from their houses and business premises. The researcher to investigate if material in-print or media forms are available to the people to educate them on how to manage the flood situation, be it from the government or any NGO. The results from field survey revealed that the sampled respondents did not have access to any material in print form, educating or sensitizing them on the hazards of flood and its causes, but they did indicate being aware or radio sensitizations from the government/ministry of environment educating them on habits causing flood and its dangers. In this respect, 100% of the respondents reported not having access to print media, while 36% reported being aware of government advert, 68% reported not being aware. This implies that efforts are being made by media houses to sensitize people about the flood. Therefore, the respondents do not have access to flood materials because the analysis shows 0% of access to flood materials. Establishing the effect of flooding on social infrastructures, the analysis shows that the 23% agreed the flooding affected schools in their LGAs, while 77% of the respondents are not aware of that incident. More so, in terms of electricity, the 65% of the respondents affirmed that flooding in their areas affected electricity, whereas 35% of the respondents it did not and non say they are not aware. Consequently, it is clear that flooding in the two LGA did not affect the hospitals. However, the LGAs have very few hospitals. On the effect of flooding on the Likelihood of the respondents the low patronages are 64% while the possibility of properties/goods loss is 36%; what is means is that government and individuals, and corporate organisations interests and attention in addressing the needs to mitigate flooding is more devastating than the loss of properties from the flood victims. In addition, in the case of the real causes of flooding in Port Harcourt and Obio-Akpor LGAs, 21% respondents agreed that refuse dumping in gutters is the issue, while 18% respondents asserted that illegal approval of building plans is responsible. Besides, 5% respondents considered inappropriate town planning as the cause. Thus, 28% and 28% respondents affirmed that poor drainages and natural flooding due to excessive rain are greatly the main causes of the flooding in Rivers State. This is confirmed the fact that is shown in the analysis of the effect of flooding on patronage of businesses, which reported that 88% of the respondents agreed that the business patronage by customers or sales were extremely poor, while respondents said there were no sales at all in the two LGAs. The types of commercial activities affected by the flood are analysed, results from the respondents show that flood activities affect 19% of retail shop owners while 16% respondents agree that 15% of flood activities affect real estate. Besides, 65% say it does not affect commercial activities. This means flooding activities though devastating but do not have overall influence on commercial activities in the LGAs.

The effect of the flood on the schools in the study area was tested using a one by two chi-square contingency analysis to test statistically the differences in the frequencies of the Yes, no options responded to by the respondents. From table 4.12.1, the results of the observed frequency shows that there is significant disparity between the observed frequencies for level of sales recorded. The Yes response has an observed frequency of 23 while the No have an observed frequency of 77. The p-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05, implying that statistically, there is significant difference between the observed and the expected. The residual (-27) for the Yes responses is negatively signed and

the frequency of the Yes response (23) is lower than the No responses (77). The researcher therefore concludes that flooding has significant effect on schools in the study area.

The effect of the flood on the power (Electricity) in the study area was tested using a one by two chi-square contingency analysis to test statistically the differences in the frequencies of the Yes, no options responded to by the respondents. From table 4.12.2, the results of the observed frequency show that there is disparity between the observed frequencies for level of sales recorded. The Yes response has an observed frequency of 61 while the No has an observed frequency of 39. The p-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.28, implying that statistically, there is no significant difference between the observed and the expected. The residual (-11.0) for the No responses is negatively signed and the frequency of the No response (39) is lower than the Yes responses (61). The researcher therefore concludes that flooding has significant effect on electricity distribution in the study area.

To ascertain the effect of the flood situation on the income of the respondents, a one by two chi-square contingency analysis was used to test statistically the differences in the level of sales recorded during the flood. From table 4.13, the results of the observed frequency show that there is significant disparity between the observed frequencies for level of sales recorded. From table 4.13, the results of the observed frequency show that there is significant disparity between the observed frequencies for poor sales and no sales options. The poor sales responses have an observed frequency of 89 while the No sales responses have an observed frequency of 19. The p-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.000, implying that statistically, there is significant difference between the observed and the expected. The residual (-31.0) for the No sales responses is negatively signed and the frequency of the No sales response (19) is lower than the poor sales responses (81). The researcher therefore concludes that flooding has significant effect on the income of the respondents in the study area (poor sales).

Table 2: Flood and Socioeconomic Wellbeing in Port Harcourt and Obio-Akpor LGAs

Effects of Flood level on Social Amenities		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Level of effect on school	Between Groups	.213	2	.106	.425	.031
	Within Groups	24.297	97	.250		
	Total	24.510	99			
Level of effect on power	Between Groups	1.205	2	.602	2.472	.002
	Within Groups	23.635	97	.244		
	Total	24.840	99			
Level of effect on income	Between Groups	.920	2	.460	1.381	.001
	Within Groups	32.320	97	.333		
	Total	33.240	99			

Source: Authors Computation from SPSS version 23

The ANOVA assessed the effects of flooding on socioeconomic development in Port Harcourt and Obio-Akpor It was conducted to determine if there is statistically significant difference between group means of flood levels effect on the basic social amenities as well as income in the study area. The results show that the flood levels effect on education (affected schools) shows a significance value (P-value) of 0.031 which is less than 0.005, therefore there is statistically significant difference in the mean flood levels and their effect of schools. Also, the flood levels effect on power (Electricity) shows a significance value (P-value) of 0.002 which is less than 0.005, therefore there is statistically significant difference in the mean flood levels and their effect of power. On income of the effect of the flood levels on the income of the respondents, the flood levels effects show a significance value (P-value) of 0.001 which is less than 0.005, therefore there is statistically significant difference in the mean flood levels and their effect on income of the respondent.

Discussion of Findings

The study examines the effect of flooding on socio - economic wellbeing of residents in Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt local government areas, Rivers State; therefore, the result revealed that there is statistically significant difference in the mean flood levels and their effect of schools. The flood has devastating effect on schools. The implication is that the citizens are often force out of school, causing education shock; thereby, increasing the level illiteracy in the affected area. The study conforms with Chiadikobi, et. al. (2011) and Emberge (2014) the flooding caused devastating effects on the socio-economic wellbeing of the citizens. In addition, the result showed that statistically significant difference exists between flood levels and power, implying that flooding cause acute power

shortage. The finding is not variance with Emberge (2014) flood risk infrastructures, enhances poverty, and so on. Furthermore, there is statistically significant difference in the mean flood levels and income of the respondents. Its implication is that considerable number of citizens are driven to poverty since the flooding inflict financial injury on their investment and other economic activities. The is agreement with Akukwe and Kohoda (2018) Chiadikobi, et al. (2011) and Emberge (2014) findings that the flooding distort food supply and distribution, economic activities and wellbeing of the citizens. However, Akukwe and Kohoda (2018) discovered that flooding inherently enhances yam production, sweet potatoes, and cavassa with other staple foods. The general implication of study is that flooding in the Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt debased the socioeconomic wellbeing of the citizens.

CONCLUSION

The study focuses on effect of flooding on socioeconomic wellbeing of residents in Port Harcourt and Obio-Akpor LGAs in Rivers State, Nigeria. The analyses revealed that residents of flood prone areas are familiar with the problems but the majority of them do not have access to radio sensitizations and material prints distributed when it occurs. The study also established that the flood affected negatively social amenities, business owners, destroyed properties, and hampered movements. Nevertheless, flooding in the caused by poor drainages and excessive rainfall overflows. This is confirmed by the fact that the effects of flooding have significant effects on school, electricity and income of businesses. It is concluded that flooding greatly makes the socioeconomic wellbeing of Rivers State citizens unbearable.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the foregoing discussions and from the findings the study recommends that there should be immediate action from both the government and citizenry as follows:

- 1) Citizens should seek approved government plans before embarking on building projects to avoid blocking natural water passages.
- 2) Deep trenches should be dug in areas where water cannot flow so as to hold water till the flood passes. This can be done by community effort or with help from the government.
- 3) All blocked drainages that have been closed due to construction should be opened.
- 4) Preparation of drainage plan and enact regulation laws or bye laws to prevent/ mitigate flooding in the study area.
- 5) Demolition of structures and buildings that can obstruct the flow of water and proper site analysis report should be made to accompany development plans.
- 6) A comprehensive drainage/infrastructure planning works program should be established for the communities by relevant authorities like ministry of urban Development, ministry of works and ministry of land and survey and so on.
- 7) A Standard Flood Operation and Emergency response plan should be enacted and put in place to cushion the effect/impact of flood on the immediate affected.
- 8) Penalty For individuals dumping refuse into sewers and desilting /de-choking of all culvert points and drains in Obio/Akpor and Port-Harcourt city Area's.

CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

This study has revealed and shed more light on the causes of flooding, both natural and man-made, the mitigation strategies and control measures. It is hoped that, the mitigating strategies and pro-active measures (routine evacuation of drainages), when properly followed will reduce significantly the devastating effects of floods in the study area.

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